

Industrial Overview of Back-to-Back VSC Power Links in MV Distribution Networks

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Abstract—This paper presents an overview of Back-to-Back VSC type power links as a promising technology, yet little deployed, to enhance the operational flexibility of MV distribution networks. It provides a technical insight of four cornerstones that Distribution System Operators could consider from a planning perspective: power electronics, backhaul network characteristics, dispatching control strategies and protection requirements. Details on power electronics and protections are given with an industrial approach, differential with information available in academic works and generic reviews. The paper showcases figures of multi-megawatt size converters and uses a real 30kV distribution network model to assess converter capacity selection and protection requirements. Additionally, different control strategies of Back-to-Back VSC power links are introduced showing the influence that backhaul network can have over them. Seen from a dispatching perspective, an overview of different control strategies is presented describing options available for MV grids that account for different digitalization levels. The overview given in this paper allows to have a clear vision of technology readiness, integration requirements and technical limitations of Back-to-Back VSC power links for its deployment in MV distribution networks.

Index Terms—Power conversion, Power distribution control, Power system communication, Power system protection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric systems have experienced changes from legacy schemes in which large centralized generators were connected to transmission networks and power was distributed downstream, towards consumers. Modern power grids tend to integrate more renewable distributed generation (DG) with a trend towards connecting it to medium voltage (MV) distribution networks [1]. This can impose power flows and voltage profiles that differ from original designs and may generate new constraints that affect the operation of MV grids. This change of paradigm has led Distribution System Operators (DSO) to avoid traditional ‘fit and forget’ strategies [2] and adopt active management techniques to optimize the use of existing grid infrastructure and increase hosting capacity [3–5].

Maximizing the use of existing grid infrastructure is fundamental to utilities that must supply reliable power to an ever more electrified society. This approach is of major importance considering the cost on money and time entailed by the construction of new power lines for the same purpose. Table I shows indicative costs of the most relevant materials to consider in the construction of a new 30kV distribution line (sourced from Group Iberdrola).

Special attention must be drawn on new overhead power line acceptance difficulties, which may imply denials, due to environmental issues or social rejection. Alternative underground layouts imply significantly higher costs and could require exploring alternative solutions that would defer such investments. In this sense, distribution level power electronics (PE) devices can help DSOs in their objective of optimizing the use of existing distribution grids.

Two main groups are identified in this field. On the one hand Custom Power devices (CP) [6] and on the other hand Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) [7]. Considering the IEEE definition of each group (Table II), CP devices are more oriented to guaranteeing power quality to end users whereas distribution level FACTS offer functionalities that are aligned with flexibility and enhanced utilization of grid infrastructure.

In the field of distribution level FACTS, five main device types are identified, each offering different characteristics in services rendered, performance metrics and sizing needs. These are:

- Static Reactive Power Compensator (STATCOM).
- Static Series Synchronous Compensator (SSSC).
- Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC) with Inter-Line (IPFC [8]) and Hybrid (HPFC [9]) variants.
- Back-to-Back Voltage Source Converter power link (B2B-VSC).
- Multi-Terminal VSC power link (MT-VSC).

Details on the characteristics of these main FACTS are described in [10] where a comparison of all options is presented from an operational perspective.

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TABLE I
30kV DISTRIBUTION POWER LINE & SUBSTATION COSTS

Concept	Cost
Power lines	
Overhead ⁽¹⁾⁽⁵⁾	(k\$/km) \approx [70 – 85]
Underground ⁽²⁾	(k\$/km) \approx [170 – 280]
Switching Substation	
<i>Protections & Measurements</i>	
Switchgears ⁽³⁾	(k\$/unit) \approx 55
Measurements ⁽⁴⁾	(k\$) \approx [250 – 300]
<i>Civil works</i>	(k\$/m ²) \approx 0.5

(¹): Single circuit equipped with LA180 conductor (see Table IV).
(²): Single circuit, equivalent AL400 cable laid in protective conduit [11].
(³): Primary MV distribution switchgears. Protection relays included.
(⁴): Average per substation, includes backup DC supply system from batteries.
(⁵): High project acceptance delays in urban areas and very high delays if environmentally protected areas are involved. Average Project acceptance delays > 12 months.

TABLE II
DISTRIBUTION LEVEL PE DEVICES – CUSTOM POWER & FACTS

Custom Power [6]	The concept of employing power electronic (static) controllers in 1 kV through 38 kV distribution systems for supplying a compatible level of power quality necessary for adequate performance of selected facilities and processes.
FACTS [7]	Alternating current transmission systems incorporating power electronic based and other static controllers to enhance controllability and increase power transfer capability.

This paper focuses on B2B-VSC type power links as the distribution level FACTS type that in the last five-year term has witnessed utility scale projects deployed in MV distribution grids [12], [13]. It complements the information given by generic reviews [14] providing a specific overview of four cornerstones that DSOs could consider from a planning perspective of such grid assets: power electronics, backhaul network characteristics, dispatching control strategies and protection requirements.

Section II introduces the technology, analyzing different power link options covered by the B2B-VSC acronyms: Soft Open Points (SOP) and Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC).

Section III provides details of power electronics and MV backhaul network characteristics. The first, power electronics, is tackled comparing figures of different multi-megawatt B2B-VSC converter options with specific details sourced from industrial designs. The information is presented in a way that could be useful for feasibility and system planning studies, covering dimensions, performance metrics and cost topics. The second, backhaul network characteristics of MV distribution grids, is introduced from an integration perspective of this type of assets into existing power systems. This approach is rarely adopted in literature but necessary to bridge the gap between access to measurements of such devices and the two remaining cornerstones, control strategies and protections.

Section IV focuses on control strategies of B2B-VSC power links proposing a two-layer sorting based on end-use or dispatching needs. End-use control strategies aimed at specific purposes are widely covered by literature but insights on

dispatching control strategies, basic from a system planning perspective, are less documented and available in unbundled references. Considered most important from an implementation point of view, section IV provides an overview of dispatching control strategies.

The fourth and last cornerstone, protections, is introduced in Section V using a real 30kV distribution grid model. Based on that, a comprehensive exercise compares protection requirements in grid reconfigurations carried out with B2B-VSC power links or standard bus-ties.

To conclude, Section VI wraps up the most relevant facts and figures discussed along the paper.

II. TYPES AND USE OF B2B-VSC POWER LINKS

Built upon bi-directional power converters that connect two AC terminals through an intermediate DC link, B2B-VSC power links can control active power flow between either AC sides as well as voltage or reactive power transfer in each one of them. The acronym ‘B2B’, makes a clear reference to the physical disposition of PE bridges and the resulting AC-DC-AC converter topology. The technology state-of-the-art enables different types of B2B-VSC power links, each fitting best to specific application characteristics. MV distribution is the field in which most research has been done and where this paper is focused.

In MV distribution networks, two types of B2B-VSC power links are used. On the one hand, the so called Soft Open Point (SOP) [15] where the B2B-VSC is built into one single converter that can be installed at a MV substation. On the other hand, the Medium Voltage Direct Current link (MVDC) [13] in which the converter is split into two separate AC/DC terminals located at different sites and connected through MV DC cables (Fig. 1). While SOP links require smaller footprints and can fit in existing substations, MVDC links take advantage of lower DC losses in medium-long distance power transfer (being possible to use existing AC infrastructure as DC lines [13], [16]).

Technical literature also refers to SOP type power links using the following technical terms and acronyms; Soft Normally Open Point (SNOP) [17], Looped Power Flow Controllers (LPFC) [18], Loop Balance Controller (LBC) [18], Flexible Power Link (FPL) [12]. Despite few references identified in real applications, research related to MV distribution B2B-VSC links has been addressed by academia and industrial players since several years now. Different works have studied various applications and end uses, such as Power Flow Control (PFC) or increase of hosting capacity among others. A list of end-use references can be found in [14].

Fig. 1: B2B-VSC power links. a) SOP type, b) MVDC type.

In LV distribution networks, a pilot project has also deployed a SOP type power link to increase flexibility of low voltage (LV) urban networks [19]. Other projects are exploring similar objectives with different technologies, such as Solid State Transformers (SST) [20]. End uses of such assets are similar to those described for MV, adapted to network topologies in LV with a higher presence of meshed architectures compared to predominantly radial MV systems. To finalize, there is a trend to explore more efficient ways for distributing power through LV grids using Low Voltage Direct Current technology (LVDC) [20], similar in concept to previously described MVDC. Other applications of B2B-VSC power links, different from utility distribution are:

- The integration of micro grids with SOP power links, mostly referred as Interlinking Converters [21].
- Renewable energy integration with MVDC power links for improved power quality [22] or for connecting distant renewable energy generation (e.g. tidal) into onshore grids [23].
- Power transfer to loads with either SOP or MVDC links. Used in industry [16], [24], railway [25] or smart ports [26]. The simpler end use of supplying power to loads enables the use of simpler power conversion solutions as unidirectional converter topologies.

III. B2B-VSC POWER LINKS IN MV DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS

The number of real power link projects deployed worldwide in distribution networks is scarce. In spite of that, one of its main applications, PFC, is included in the list of grid modernization plans [27]. Nevertheless, to date, only a few initiatives are identified in real distribution grids, all built upon B2B-VSC or MT-VSC topologies. Among them, MV distribution networks account for the most relevant utility scale projects [12], [13]. According to the authors' best knowledge, references indicated in Table III represent the list of distribution level power links installed internationally.

Next paragraphs provide details of industrial PE designs suitable for configuring utility scale B2B-VSC power links and backhaul network characteristics in MV distribution networks.

TABLE III
DISTRIBUTION LEVEL POWER LINK REFERENCES

Type	MV/ LV	Year	Location	Volt. Power	Ref.
SOP	MV	2003	Germany	10kV 2MVA	[28]
SOP	MV	2007	Japan	6.6kV 1MVA	[18]
B2B-VSC	SOP	LV	UK	<1kV <1MVA	[19]
SOP	MV	2017	UK	33kV 20MVA	[12]
MVDC	MV	2020	UK	33kV 30MVA	[13]
MT-VSC	SOP	MV	-	China 11kV 4x1MVA	[29]

A. Power Electronics

Maturity and proven in use reliability of PE technology can be considered an enabling factor for the use of B2B-VSC power links in MV distribution networks. The following sub-sections deal with the capacity selection and technology of power converters used in this type of applications.

1) Capacity selection of B2B-VSC converters

Previously referred utility scale projects [12], [13], opted for determining B2B-VSC converter capacities that matched the thermal rating of MV power lines. Whereas the converter capacity of [13] was defined to maximize the power transfer capacity of an AC circuit converted to MVDC, the converter used in [12] was defined considering the thermal rating of the AC lines that would be interconnected by the SOP link [30]. This straightforward capacity selection criterion can be valid in radial systems where the rating of standard MV distribution circuits (Table IV) can be achieved with state-of-the-art PE converters, as it is further discussed in this paper. Moreover, from a planning perspective, increasing electric power demand could also justify grid reinforcements through B2B-VSC power links that would cover future needs making full use of the existing grid infrastructure.

In meshed systems, where grid architecture is more complex, B2B-VSC capacity selection might require specific integration studies considering the end use of the power link to be installed (e.g., hosting capacity). This scenario is described in the example that is presented in Fig. 2 and detailed in Table V, based on a real MV distribution grid built upon a double overhead 30kV circuit (i.e. Line1 and Line 2, equipped with LA180 type conductor). This circuit connects two Bulk Supply Points (BSP) where four circuit heads are installed (i.e., A, B, C and D) rated to 22.4MVA each. The full circuit serves power to more than 40,000 customers including two industrial generators connected to both lines. It must be noted that the original grid model has been simplified in Fig. 2 for representation purposes.

The capacity of the industrial generators is currently limited to 18MW each to keep line voltages within maximum allowed values (≤ 1.07 p.u.) in the worst-case scenario that corresponds to low load conditions. Hosting capacity could be increased should an intermediate ring be configured in the MV circuit allowing for optimized voltage profiles. This intermediate ring could be physically configured at Substation 1 by installing a B2B-VSC power link between both lines.

TABLE IV
SINGLE CIRCUIT OVERHEAD DISTRIBUTION LINE STANDARD RATING [31]

Voltage (kV)	Conductor Section (S) (mm ²)	Conductor Type (EN 50182)	Ampacity (A _{RMS})	3-phase Power (MVA)
20	94.2	94-AL1/LA110	318	11
	147.3	147-AL1/LA180	431	14.9
30	94.2	94-AL1/LA110	318	16.5
	147.3	147-AL1/LA180	431	22.4
	241.6	242-AL1/LA280	581	30.1

TABLE V
DATA OF 30kV MV DISTRIBUTION MESHED GRID

Characteristic	Data
Circuit length – Full Circuit (all branches) (km)	151
Number of Nodes (units)	226
Load – Peak / Valley conditions (MW)	45 / 15

Using PSS/E simulation environment and Python SciPy optimization library, the optimal B2B-VSC converter capacity has been determined to maximize generation capacity of both industrial generators whilst seeking for minimum overall system losses (i.e., sum of all circuit branch losses) (1).

$$f \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \max \text{Generation}_{[Line 1, Line 2]} \\ \min \sum \text{Loss}_{branch [1-n]} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

This nested objective function has been solved considering operation constraints that limit the maximum loading of any grid branch (2), as well as the maximum voltage measured at any grid node (3).

$$\text{Loading}_{branch [1-n]} < 100 \% \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Voltage}_{node [1-m]} \leq 1.07 \text{ p.u.} \quad (3)$$

Finally, the optimization algorithm has found the optimal active ($P_{B2B-VSC}$) and reactive power ($Q_{B2B-VSC [Line 1, Line 2]}$) dispatch of a candidate B2B-VSC converter which maximum apparent power value ($S_{max B2B-VSC}$) has been defined to the rating of the 30kV circuit heads (i.e. 22.4MVA) (4),(5).

$$Q_{max B2B-VSC} = \max (|Q_{B2B-VSC [Line 1]}|, |Q_{B2B-VSC [Line 2]}|) \quad (4)$$

$$\sqrt{P_{B2B-VSC}^2 + Q_{max B2B-VSC}^2} \leq 22.4 \text{ MVA} = S_{max B2B-VSC} \quad (5)$$

The optimization exercise has been carried out for the valley load scenario defined in Table V.

Results obtained show that the use of a B2B-VSC power link has allowed to increase hosting capacity to values that are above 35MW. The B2B-VSC converter maximum apparent power (S) required for that has proved to be 15 MVA, i.e., $\approx 33\%$ lower than the initially allowed full line rating capacity of 22.4MVA. Fig. 3 depicts optimal P and Q dispatch values determined by the optimization exercise as well as the resulting capacity of the B2B-VSC converter.

Fig. 2: 30kV meshed grid reconfiguration with SOP type B2B-VSC.

Fig. 3: SOP type B2B-VSC capacity selection in 30kV meshed grid.

The following section describes the PE technology that is available in the market to configure B2B-VSC converters that would cover previously discussed capacity needs.

2) B2B-VSC converter technology

Among different options available, MV PE arises as the adequate technology to build B2B-VSC links that could fit previously discussed capacity ratings of B2B-VSC converters. This is the approach that has been followed in the referred projects [12], [13] rated to 20 and 30 MVA respectively.

Advances in power semiconductor technology have boosted power density values of LV converters (Table VI). However, considering the rest of components that are part of a B2B-VSC power link (i.e., grid coupling transformers and related wiring), MV solutions show best efficiency and lowest overall costs. All in all, makes MV PE technology most suitable to reach power ratings mentioned.

When it comes to topologies, two main designs rule the market of commercially available MV converters suitable for building utility scale B2B-VSC power links:

- Neutral Point Clamp (NPC), long proven in industry and available for different variants [32]. This is the topology of the PE building blocks used in [12] and [13].
- Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC), widely used in transmission level power converters, such as HVDC, and adapted to MV applications [33], [34].

Other MV PE topologies, technically valid but with lower commercial adoption can be found in the technical literature [35].

A comparison of type values of different 10MVA water-cooled converters valid to be used as SOP links is shown in Table VI and Table VII. They provide industrial figures on key characteristics describing state of the art LV and MV converters sourced from internal product portfolio of [36]. All compared designs include in-built sinusoidal harmonic filters at each AC connection terminals. Required cooling unit elements (e.g., redundant pumps) are also considered in the footprint values given for all options.

Scaling solutions towards higher power values can be achieved by parallelizing MV converters. With this approach, some converter components (e.g., filters) can be optimized allowing for higher efficiencies. Wise combinations of MV converters with grid coupling transformers must be used for that; multi-winding and phase-shifted transformers as well as optimized semiconductor modulation techniques. In principle, LV solutions could benefit from same savings, but unavoidable current values entail higher costs and require outstanding numbers of power semiconductors.

TABLE VI
10MVA WATER-COOLED SOP CONVERTERS (I)
CONVERTER & TRANSFORMER TYPE DATA

		CONVERTER DATA		
		SOP Converter Type		
Data		LV 2L-VSC	3.3kV MV 3L-NPC Fig. 5	6.6kV MV 3L-NPC [32] Fig. 4
AC Voltage	(kV)	0.69	3.3	6.6
Converter DC Voltage	(kV)	1.1	5.1	10.2
Output current	(Arms)	8400	1800	875
Footprint LxW	(m)	5.2x1.2	6.5x1.2	6.5x1.2
Power Density	(MVA/m ²)	1.6	1.28	1.28
Semiconductors	(Number)	72	24	48
	(Type)	LV-IGBT	IGCT	MV-IGBT
		Infineon FF1400R 17IP4	ABB 5SHY35L 4520	Hitachi MBN1500 FH45F
		TRANSFORMER DATA		
General (All)		Oil type, air-natural cooling (ONAN) Primary MV voltage, 30kV		
Type				
Number of units (**)		2x2 (5MVA)	1x2 (10MVA)	1x2 (10MVA)
		OVERALL COSTS (CAPEX Electric components)		
	TOTAL	100	95	93
Cost (%)	Converter	18	8	7
	Transformer	21	27	25
	Wiring (***)	61	65	69

(*): For constructive and safety reasons (i.e., short-circuit strength), it is recommended to limit the maximum current through individual winding (<4000A, typically).
(**): Possibility of building the two (x2) required power transformers into one single tank, cost and space savings, approach used in [12].
(***) Includes copper unipolar power wiring and MV switchgears for transformer primary winding protection.

TABLE VII
10MVA WATER-COOLED SOP CONVERTERS (II)
CONVERTER SHARE OF LOSSES & EFFICIENCY DATA

The exercise illustrated in Table VIII compares two ways of configuring a 30MVA SOP link based on the 6.6kV converter option introduced in Table VI. Referred as Standard and Enhanced options, the first describes a pure parallel connection of 10MVA SOP converters to standard transformers. The second, proposes an enhanced combination of similar units including optimized filters (dV/dt type instead of sinusoidal) and phase-shifted multi-winding transformers. Such transformers, used in other applications (i.e., industry, multi-pulse transformers), can be optimized to include an auxiliary winding to connect grid harmonic filters, when required, avoiding the installation of such components at the 30kV switchyard. The latter would permit to adopt solutions that can be fully integrated in electrical rooms and tested before shipment, allowing for reduced installation and commissioning times.

Fig. 4: 6.6kV MV 3L-NPC SOP converter (MV900 in [36])

Fig. 5: 3.3kV MV 3L-NPC SOP converter (MV500 in [36])

The use of dV/dt filters reduces considerably current sizing needs of passive components installed in converters (e.g., inductors), boosting efficiency values thereof. Instead, filtering elements, necessary to comply with power quality standards, must be embedded into the power transformer imposing a higher short-circuit impedance. Moreover, insulation and thermal constraints must be carefully addressed to cope with pulsed voltage waveforms and presence of current harmonics. Data from finite element simulations of a similar multi-winding transformer (sized to 37/50MVA oil type Natural/Forced cooling and including a filtering winding) has been used to estimate efficiency values declared in Table VIII and Table IX. Based on that, a (D) type transformer would have 40% more losses than a (B) type transformer, motivated by the higher short-circuit impedance (20% losses) and the higher harmonic burden (20% losses). A breakdown of total losses is depicted in Fig. 6.

TABLE VIII
30MVA SOP BASED ON 6.6kV MV 3L-NPC CONVERTER

- (A): Converter in-built sinusoidal filter.
 (B): Single winding 30MVA YN / Δ transformer.
 (C): Converter in-built dV/dt filter.
 (D): Multiple winding 30MVA YN / Δ (-20°/0°/20°) power transformer.
 (E): Grid harmonic filter installed at 30kV switchyard.
 (F): Grid harmonic filter installed at transformer auxiliary winding (15kV).

NOTE: E and F are complementary options. Data below is given considering option F for grid harmonic mitigation.

Metrics		Power Scaling Option	
		Standard	Enhanced
Converter footprint LxW	(m)	3x[6.5x1.2]	3x[4.6x1.2]
Grid harmonic filter LxW	(m)	in-built	2x[3.0x1.2]
Efficiency (%)	Converters	97.9	98.74
	Grid harm. filters	-	-0.15 (*)
	Transformers	99.6	99.45
	TOTAL	97.11	97.5

(*): Represented as loss of efficiency (percent) for the overall solution.

Fig. 6. Losses breakdown in a D type multiple winding transformer.

TABLE IX
30MVA SOP BASED ON 6.6kV MV 3L-NPC CONVERTER –
STANDARD & ENHANCED SOLUTIONS - EFFICIENCY DATA

B. Backhaul network of MV distribution grids

Low visibility is a prevailing characteristic of MV distribution grids. Whereas LV distribution grids have undergone a significant roll-out of smart meters [37], MV distribution grids still account for low digitalization levels. With very little information available from utilities, different studies identify that less than 20% of transformer substations are monitored in MV distribution grids [38], [39].

Low grid visibility implies limited access to key information (i.e., voltage levels and power flows) to acquire an adequate situational awareness and make right decisions on available assets such as B2B-VSC power links. Apart from having access to measurements, accuracy, and real-time availability thereof (or close to) are determining factors to permit rapid reactions to system variabilities. In this sense, the communication network that links MV substations with control centers (i.e., backhaul network) is of utmost importance.

Predominantly based on Remote Terminal Units (RTU), and related SCADA systems, MV grids automation relies on signal sampling rates that range for seconds, at best [39]. The advent of Phasor Measuring Units (PMU) in transport systems and its adaption to distribution grids through so called micro PMUs (μ PMU), showcases future improvements yet to come [40]. An

effective integration of such assets, capable of delivering measurements sampled in the range of milliseconds, will only be possible with backhaul networks that support such burdensome data streams.

A summary of available backhaul options in MV distribution grids is shown in Table X detailing its average use in Rural (R) and Urban (U) areas [39]. The information is completed with a suitability assessment of each option considering its potential use in control centers that should integrate fast measurements to determine optimal dispatching of B2B-VSC power links. The criteria used for that is based on the following performance requirements: Throughput (Thr), Latency (Lat) and Reliability (Rel) [41], [42].

It is worthwhile to mention the possibilities that cellular 5G communications could offer in the near future to enhance the capacity of MV distribution backhaul [43]. 5G technology shows highest performance characteristics and entails lower deployment costs than new O.F. lines, postulating this technology as an enabling factor to overcome actual limitations.

Table XI provides comparison figures of O.F. and 5G sourced from [41], [42].

IV. CONTROL STRATEGIES OF B2B-VSC POWER LINKS

Similar to backhaul networks, control strategies used in B2B-VSC power links are critical to enable an effective and safe integration of such assets into MV distribution grids. Literature identifies various control techniques aimed at different end uses [14]. Many of them rely on ideal backhaul networks that allow for limitless availability of measurements. Nevertheless, previously described factors entail unavoidable constraints to the scope and real time execution of such control techniques.

To better assess the wide range of control strategies available, this paper proposes a two-layer nesting, differentiated according to:

- Use made of the backhaul network, referred as dispatching layer.
- Final purpose of measurements sourced from backhaul network, referred as end-use layer.

TABLE X
BACKHAUL NETWORK IN MV DISTRIBUTION GRIDS

Backhaul network options	Use [%] U / R	Suitability assessment		
		Thr.	Lat.	Rel.
WiFi, WiMax	- / 13	↑	↑	↓↓
Radio	25 / 50	↓	↓	↓↓
Cellular (GPRS, 4G)	58 / 75	↑	↑	↑
Optical Fiber (O.F.)	38 / 46	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑
Power Line Carrier (PLC)	4 / 21	-	-	↓
Copper	27 / 30	↑	↑	↑

TABLE XI
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON BETWEEN OPTIC FIBER AND 5G

	Throughput (Gbps)	Latency (ms)
O.F.	10	100-150
5G	20	<1

The end-use layer is composed by different control techniques aimed at specific purposes. On the other hand, the dispatching layer is composed by three control strategies which are sorted according to dependence towards backhaul network. From highest to lowest in backhaul dependence ranking, these are:

- Centralized Control.
- Communication Fault Tolerant control.
- Autonomous control.

Both layers are hierarchically dependent, as shown in Table XII. In this way, a specific dispatching strategy can host multiple end-use controls, but an individual end-use control is tailored for a specific purpose and depends on data sourced by the dispatching layer.

Most papers describing controls of B2B-VSC power links tend to focus on details of end-use algorithms whereas a smaller number disclose insights of dispatching controls used. Next paragraphs gather the most representative references of dispatching controls used in MV distribution grids, detailing examples of research studies and real applications as well as describing efforts made to minimize dependence towards backhaul networks.

A. Centralized Control

It is based on a central controller that gathers all measurements required by end-use controls to determine the right dispatching of the B2B-VSC power link. Measurements are bounded to the grid area in which the power link will have an influence, hence, backhaul burden depends on the extension of the grid, closely tied to the node number and distances to be considered.

An example of a centralized control recently commissioned in a real application corresponds to the SOP type power link described in [12]. The device connects two substations that so far supplied independent 33kV circuits, one presenting high levels of distributed generation and the other being dominated by consumer loads. Specific backhaul infrastructure has been set up among eight distant substations installed in the target influence area. Through the communication links set, the central controller receives real-time data of the variables that characterize the status of the grid (i.e., voltages and load flows) and calculates active and reactive power set points (P, Q) of the SOP link. Despite good performance in normal conditions, contingencies with backhaul network can constrain the performance, accuracy and even the operation of the power link.

TABLE XII
HIERARCHY OF CONTROL STRATEGIES IN B2B-VSC POWER LINKS

Layer	Control Strategies		
DISPATCHING	Centralized Control	Communication Fault Tolerant Control	Autonomous Control
END-USE [14]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power flow control. • Network re-configuration. • Feeder load balancing. • Distribution losses minimization. • Increase of hosting capacity. • Power supply restoration (+ others) 		

B. Communication Fault-tolerant Control

A Communication Fault Tolerant (CFT) control strategy, as its name might suggest, is tailored to overcome problems generated by backhaul network contingencies.

Based on a centralized control, a CFT variant is illustrated in [44] where lacking measurements caused by interrupted communications in a SOP type power link, are replaced by real-time estimated values obtained from variable observers. In this manner, the original centralized dispatching control can be kept invariant regardless of backhaul availability, switching the source of input data from measured to estimated. Referred as Centralized Fallback control (C-Fallback), the technique is tested also for a different communication contingency in which network measurements are supposed to be available for end-use algorithms but calculated set points dispatching channels are off-service. In this case, the paper proposes an alternative control method where dispatching values of the SOP are defined through historic voltage and power flow patterns stored locally in the SOP converter controller. Although this alternative could work in ideal scenarios where reality matches historic patterns, the authors suggest that network operation variability can deeply affect the performance of the proposed method.

A different CFT approach is adopted in [45] where the control strategy was designed from the beginning to minimize backhaul requirements. Coined as Grid Transformer based control (GT-based) and used in the MVDC link that is referred in [13], it only measures power flow values from two distant HV/MV bulk supply transformers. With this information and additional data sourced from offline calculations (response curves), the MVDC is dispatched to achieve its end-use objectives. The CFT feature of this control comes from the fact that measurements, reduced in number, are communicated to the dispatching control by dedicated links.

C. Autonomous Control

A fully autonomous control, completely unaffected by backhaul network relies on local measurements taken at the AC terminals of the B2B-VSC power link and directly wired to its controller.

The work presented in [46] describes a SOP link that is operated emulating a bus-tie switch hence, driving to zero the difference in amplitude and angle of voltage phasors in both AC terminals of the SOP. Referred as switch mode control, it does not allow for a direct dispatch of active and reactive power as both magnitudes will be set indirectly according to voltage magnitudes and power angle values.

It is worth mentioning that literature covers more references of autonomous controls designed for transmission grids (HVDC). An example of the latter is the AC Transmission line Emulation Control (ATEC) that is described in [47]. As its acronyms might suggest, ATEC allows for the operation of a DC power link as a virtual AC line, permitting an enhanced operation during contingencies. ATEC control operates using the information that is contained in the voltage phasors (\vec{V}_1, \vec{V}_2) measured at both AC terminals of the HVDC link. Hence, the

active power reference of the power link ($P_{REF_{HVDC}}$) is defined through the expression:

$$P_{REF_{HVDC}} = \frac{V_1 V_2}{X} \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) \quad (1)$$

Sub-indices linked to the voltage phasors, including amplitude (V_1, V_2) and angle (θ_1, θ_2), refer to each one of the AC terminals. On the other hand, X corresponds to the impedance (simplified to a pure inductor) of the AC line that is emulated by the ATEC control.

This control method presents a variant in the technical literature that is referred as Angle Difference Control (ADC) used in [48]. A similar case is identified in the US where ATEC was implemented as a fallback control in a HVDC link with both terminals located at the same substation [49].

ADC type controls could be explored at MV distribution grids considering topological similarities between HVDC and B2B-VSC power links. Nevertheless, unavoidable differences between transmission and distribution grids would require a detailed analysis of the angle difference evolution that is expected between the selected connection nodes. Shorter circuit lengths in MV distribution grids may suggest smaller angle differences than in transmission grids, requiring high precision measurements to be able to perform an accurate ADC control.

Previously mentioned PMUs represent the state-of-the-art of measurement technology applied to grids. The IEC standard in this field [50] defines the Total Vector Error (TVE) concept to determine the accuracy that can be expected in voltage or current phasor measurements. TVE combines magnitude and angle errors into a single quantity combining all PMU internal error sources. For a M class PMU (i.e. Measurement), the aforementioned standard defines a TVE value of $\leq 1\%$ which is usually adopted by commercial devices [51], [52]. This value implies a phase measurement uncertainty of $\pm 0.573^\circ$, hereinafter referred as $\epsilon\theta_{max}$. It is possible to specify higher accuracy PMUs defining smaller angle estimation errors. For example, Annex G of the standard [49] defines A1.0 (Am1 Ph0.1) type PMU in which; TVE is 1.0%, amplitude error is 1% maximum and phase error is 0.1° maximum ($\epsilon\theta_{min}$).

In addition to this, accuracy of measurement voltage transformers (VT) will also have an impact on the overall angle measurement uncertainty. As a reference, the IEC standard for VTs [53], defines a phase angle estimation error of $\pm 0.0859^\circ$ for a class 0.1 type VT (hereinafter, $\epsilon\theta_{0.1VT}$).

To determine the impact that these measurement errors might have on an ADC control, an exercise has been carried out considering the same meshed 30kV grid that has been used in the capacity selection study presented in Section III.A.1). In this case, a power generation sweep has been carried out in both industrial generators considering the original grid architecture, i.e., without configuring any intermediate ring (Fig. 7). During this process, the angle difference ($\Delta\theta$) measured between both lines at Substation 1 (6) has been recorded. The exercise has been carried out for valley load conditions described in Table V.

Fig. 7: Angle Difference ($\Delta\theta$) measurement during generation sweep.

$$\Delta\theta = \theta_{Terminal1} - \theta_{Terminal2} \quad (6)$$

Results presented in Fig. 8 show that, for a portion of the generation sweep, the evolution of $\Delta\theta$ is within the uncertainty zone generated by measurements accuracy. The same figure depicts two different uncertainty zones, each calculated for maximum and minimum PMU angle measurement errors, $\varepsilon\theta_{max}$ and $\varepsilon\theta_{min}$ respectively. VT accuracy has been considered constant at $\varepsilon\theta_{0.1VT}$ in all cases. The width of each uncertainty zone is calculated considering the worst case in which angle measurements at both terminals (i.e., $\theta_{Terminal1}$ and $\theta_{Terminal2}$) add the maximum error to $\Delta\theta$ (7), (8).

$$\min \Delta\theta \text{ uncertainty} = 2 \times (|\varepsilon\theta_{min}| + |\varepsilon\theta_{0.1VT}|) = 0.3718^\circ \quad (7)$$

$$\max \Delta\theta \text{ uncertainty} = 2 \times (|\varepsilon\theta_{max}| + |\varepsilon\theta_{0.1VT}|) = 1.3178^\circ \quad (8)$$

For representation purposes, Fig 8 represents uncertainty zones centered on $\Delta\theta=0^\circ$ but this error band can be transferred to any other $\Delta\theta$ value.

Fig. 8: $\Delta\theta$ measured during generation sweep in Line 1 and Line 2.

Highest precision measurements allowing for $\varepsilon\theta_{min}$ and $\varepsilon\theta_{0.1VT}$, permit to minimize the blind zone over the $\Delta\theta$ surface that is depicted in Fig.8, suggesting that ADC controls could be implemented in MV distribution grids. For that, external PMUs or embedded VSC controllers, used for measuring purposes, should guarantee this accuracy. Further research could permit to define the impact that previously defined angle measurement errors would have on the dispatching set points of a B2B-VSC power link and weight its effect on the operation of the MV grid.

To conclude, it is worth saying that real measurement errors would certainly be lower than the worst-case scenario that has been considered in the study. This would reduce the width of the uncertainty zones. The meshed grid model used in the previous exercise represents a restrictive scenario from a $\Delta\theta$ estimation perspective. As depicted in Fig. 7, distances among all nodes are within a few tens of kilometers with common BSPs at both line terminals. Other types of meshed circuits and especially radial grids branched from different BSPs might present higher $\Delta\theta$ values. Further research in this field would permit to verify the latter.

D. Dispatching Control Strategies Summary

Table XIII summarizes the main characteristics of the dispatching strategies that have been assessed in section IV. It is worth saying that centralized dispatching control is the option that, when affordable, should show best performance from a grid operation perspective motivated by accuracy and number of measurements available. However, performance metrics among different control strategies are not compared in Table XIII as all described controls have been analyzed for different case studies and there is not a common framework where results can be compared. A comparison of all identified dispatching controls within a common framework would be required to present an objective assessment of all options This work would remain pending for further research.

V. PROTECTION REQUIREMENTS OF B2B-VSC POWER LINKS

A twofold approach is proposed to assess protections requirements related to the integration of B2B-VSC power links in MV distribution grids. On the one hand, protections related to PE converters and on the other, power system protections executed by relays.

TABLE XIII
DISPATCHING CONTROL STRATEGIES SUMMARY TABLE

Control Type	A	B	C	D
Centralized [12]	Low	No	High	Yes
C-Fallback [44]	Low	Med.	Low	Yes
GT-based [45]	Med.	Med.	Med.	Yes
Switch Mode [46]	High	High	High	No
ATEC [47]	High	High	High	Yes

A: Implementation simplicity.

B: Tolerance to Comms. loss.

C: Adaptability to grid contingencies

D: Power Flow control.

A. Power electronics converter protections

PE converters controlled by digital controllers embed numerous protective functions to prevent damage face to uncontrolled situations (e.g., voltage dips or short-circuits, among others). Together with internal protections that can act over fast blocking semiconductors AC circuit breakers used to protect power transformers must ensure fast interruption times, below 100ms. This value is achievable with state-of-the-art circuit breakers available in the market but must be carefully addressed should a B2B-VSC power link be installed in an existing substation, using available MV switchgears.

Apart from self-protective functions, B2B-VSC converters offer ancillary services that can positively contribute to MV grids protection, quality of supply and security. The following paragraphs describe four main examples of the latter: Fault Ride Through (FRT) during line faults, negative sequence current control, fault diagnosis capability and system insulation strength testing functionality.

1) Fault ride through during line faults

Grid codes usually refer to generators when defining FRT requirements of converter based systems [54]. FRT capability is described as the ability of such assets to remain connected under abnormal voltage or frequency transients. Additionally, the definition is extended with the capability of injecting currents that support the operation of protection relays. B2B-VSC power links cannot be considered generation converters but being built upon similar PE technology, offer similar FRT characteristics. A comprehensive review of FRT duties of SOP converters is presented in [14].

Considering the supply restoration end use mentioned in Table XII, B2B-VSC power links are called to include additional grid supporting services that would require FRT capabilities. A B2B-VSC converter, transferring power from the healthy terminal to the faulted one, could energize a grid portion that has been isolated due to a load fault. The latter could be done through a cold load pickup [55] which implies a transition from power flow control to supply restoration mode. Nevertheless, recent trends in converter control algorithms rely on grid forming control techniques [54] that would permit a seamless transfer between both operation modes. This approach has been studied in SOP applications [56] and requires a solid FRT capability of the B2B-VSC converter to saturate output currents during this load transfer transient [57].

2) Negative sequence current control

Distribution grids are ruled by standards that define a maximum permanent voltage unbalance degree (VUD). As indicated in [58], VUD in public utilities should be less than 2% for 95% of the time. However, higher amplitude transient unbalances may occur, especially during grid faults which are predominantly unsymmetrical (mostly, single phase to ground [59]). Either in permanent or transient conditions, the negative sequence current control capability of B2B-VSC power converters can contribute to minimize the voltage unbalance of the grid. This feature is already addressed by international grid codes that require a negative sequence reactive power

absorption from grid tied converters to minimize the amplitude of negative sequence voltage [60]. The latter is possible by means of dual positive-negative sequence controls, widely used in distributed generation [61]. From a converter design and protection perspective, negative sequence current controls imply a second order harmonic voltage ripple in the converter dc link. Under distorted conditions, this voltage ripple attains higher values as described in [62], something that should be considered since early design steps of the B2B-VSC converter considering its final application use.

3) Fault diagnosis capability

Previously described seamless transfer would not be possible should a MV line be affected by a permanent fault. When protection relays trip a MV line circuit breaker, utilities program a number of reclosing tries before the fault is considered permanent. At this point, supply is interrupted and manual intervention is required to locate the fault and restore the system. This usually requires a trial-and-error approach to identify the possible area in which the fault is located. Long distance circuits are usually equipped with intermediate load breakers that can be opened (sometimes remotely, others manually) to generate partial divisions of the MV circuit and facilitate the identification of faulted areas (Fig. 9-a).

Once partitioned, fault location is carried out by energizing the MV line portion that remains connected to the circuit head. Each energization implies subjecting the system to its rated voltage. Depending on the fault impedance, each energization try can imply a high short-circuit current flow through the circuit, affecting its weakest parts, e.g., jumpers, as depicted in Fig. 9-b.

The same fault location procedure could be carried out in a much smoother manner should the circuit be energized by a B2B-VSC power link operated as a controlled voltage source. The faulted MV circuit could be gradually energized with a controlled amplitude voltage waveform until the current measured in any of the MV circuit phases would reach a predetermined value (e.g., 1.0 p.u.) (Fig. 10-a). At this point the B2B-VSC converter could perform diagnosis calculations to identify faulted phases and eventually carry out fault distance estimations.

Fig. 9: MV distribution line elements a) Load breakers b) Jumpers

Fig. 10: MV grid energization through B2B-VSC converter
a) Fault diagnosis / b) System insulation strength testing

4) System insulation strength testing

When a MV distribution circuit has undergone modifications of hardware elements, depending on the extent of the latter, specific system checks can be recommended. From an insulation strength point of view, MV circuits cannot be tested unless specific voltage sources are deployed for that purpose. B2B-VSC power links connected to the MV grid through step-up transformers equipped with tap changers (TC) (preferably On Load Tap Changers, OLTC) could be used for applying a temporary overvoltage combining maximum converter voltage modulation limit and transformer tap changer contribution.

As an example, the 6.6kV MV 3L-NPC SOP type converter that has been described in Table VI, including third harmonic injection, could synthesize a maximum no-load line-line RMS voltage ($V_{VSC \max L-L}$) of 7.21 kV at its terminals (9) [63].

$$V_{VSC \max L-L} = \frac{V_{DC \text{ B2B-VSC}}}{\sqrt{2}} \times \sqrt{3} \times \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} = 7212 \text{ V} \quad (9)$$

This converter overvoltage capability could be increased at MV side by means of the transformer TC allowing for controlled system insulation tests on the MV circuit (Fig. 10-b).

B. Power system protections

1) Protective relays

When it comes to power system protections executed by relays, is the absence of specific requirements in that sense what makes this topic an enabling factor by itself. As other PE based assets (e.g., PV inverters), B2B-VSC power links are characterized by a low fault current contribution (i.e., short-circuit current), which is fully controlled and bounded to design limits of converter hardware. Liquid cooled converters, as those presented in Table IV, usually have short-circuit current values of around 1.5 p.u. for a reduced interval (below 2s). Air-cooled designs in either LV or MV, can attain higher values, up to 2.5 p.u., with the advantage of being able to maintain this output current longer (above 10s). Different thermal inertia of power electronics (including cooling plates or radiators) is at the origin of such differences between both technologies.

Thanks to the low short-circuit contribution of B2B-VSC type power links, compared to other grid assets as synchronous machines, a network reconfiguration between two radial systems would be possible without altering original short-circuit current values [55] hence, without modifying existing instantaneous and time-delayed overcurrent relay protections. Compared to that, the same reconfiguration carried out by SSSC or UPFC type power links, would increase short-circuit currents to values attained with closed bus ties. The latter would require a feasibility assessment from the point of view of components strength and relay settings.

Should a system reconfiguration be required in a meshed system, additional details must be considered to compare implications of traditional bus-tie or B2B-VSC based reconfiguration options. This is best represented with the example that has been presented in Section III.A.1) (Fig. 2) based on a real double 30kV circuit. As previously introduced, the capacity of the industrial generators could be increased should an intermediate ring be configured in the MV circuit allowing for optimized voltage profiles. This intermediate ring could be set by closing an already available bus-tie placed at Substation 1, so far operated in open state as shown in Fig.11.

From a protection scheme perspective, currently, HV/MV Bulk Supply Points (BSP-1 and BSP-2), are equipped with directional protection relays at headers A, B, C and D allowing for a safe grid operation when both Line 1 and Line 2 are operated as a single ring; that is to say, connected through BSP-1 and BSP-2.

Considering that substation 1 bus-tie would be closed as depicted in Fig. 12, should a short-circuit occur close to the center of Line 1 (or Line 2), directional protection relays in ABCD heads would all detect a fault condition due to the short-circuit currents set (#1, #2, #3, #4). As a result, circuit breakers in ABCD heads would trip interrupting power supply to all customers. Unacceptable from a grid operation point of view, a different protection scheme should be adopted for that: the differential line protection. The latter should be configured among sub-feeders identified in Fig. 12, (A-F-C) and (B-E-D), requiring fast communication links such as F.O. to ensure a correct protection coordination.

Fig. 11: Meshed system reconfiguration option through bus-tie.

It must be noted that the implementation of differential protection schemes in tapped lines (as it is the case), entails additional difficulties due to the fact that they must coexist (and still be robust) with tapped consumers which can be relevant in MV distribution networks [64]. In overall, the system reconfiguration through a bus-tie closing would require significant modifications on relay protection schemes, which in addition, are dependent on backhaul network available.

Compared to the previous scenario, the same intermediate ring could be configured by means of a B2B-VSC SOP type power link installed between E and F (Fig. 13). Moreover, the latter would be possible without altering existing directional relay protections. Should the same short-circuit event occur, controllers embedded in the SOP link would detect the anomaly and react to avoid any short-circuit current through terminals E-F. Short-circuit current #3 represented in Fig. 13 would present lower values than #1 and #2 due to a longer flow path. This allows to carry out a robust protection selectivity compared to short-circuit current flows #1 and #2.

Additionally, the directional protection in header D would discriminate an overcurrent condition generated by short-circuit current flow #3 due to reverse direction. Consequently, protections in headers A-C would react adequately, isolating only the line under fault hence, minimizing the impact on customers and allowing for the desired reconfiguration without altering any protection scheme.

Fig. 12: Meshed system reconfiguration through a bus-tie – Fault current flows.

Fig. 13: Meshed system reconfiguration through a B2B-VSC SOP – Fault current flows.

A comparison of both reconfiguration alternatives can be done considering that the grid is equipped with the required F.O. backhaul that enables implementing a differential line protection (87L). Otherwise, backhaul upgrading costs would be too high to be considered in this exercise. To better address figures given in Table XIV, it must be noted that the differential line protection upgrade considered in this case implies the substitution of substation elements at BSPs and tapping connections across the MV circuit. The latter implies switchgears as well as Measurement and Protection devices (M&P). This approach is necessary considering that the protection upgrade would be carried out on a MV circuit that is in operation for several decades. Moreover, safety and minimum commissioning times must be carefully addressed. Both aspects have been considered at the time of selecting pre-assembled & tested elements, such as switchgears including in-built M&P that would replace some legacy outdoor MV components. The comparison that is presented in Table XIV shows that both solutions are similar in costs with only a 7% higher estimation for the 87L solution.

To broaden the scope of the comparison, both cases have been simulated to determine hosting capacity values attained in each case. The B2B-VSC option has been simulated with the same optimization algorithm described in Section III.A.1), in this case, adapted to a 6.6kV 10MVA SOP type converter (Table IV). Regarding the bus-tie option, a connection rated to the conductor maximum value of 22.4MVA has been configured between terminals 1 and 2 of substation 1 (Fig. 12). As in previous exercises, simulations have been carried out for the valley load scenario defined in Table V (worst-case in terms of voltage profiles and hosting capacity). Results are showcased in Fig 14. where the B2B-VSC option attains a 60% wider area of possible solutions within the complete simulation sweep. This is motivated by the voltage control capability that the B2B-VSC power link has, which contributes to minimize the maximum voltage measured at any node of the circuit under study.

TABLE XIV
COST COMPARISON BETWEEN B2B-VSC & 87L DIFF. LINE PROTECTION
APPLIED TO FIG 12 AND FIG 13 SCENARIOS

Concepts & %Cost breakdown		Comparison
SOP type 10MVA B2B-VSC Power Link⁽¹⁾		
PE ⁽¹⁾ & Enclosure ⁽²⁾	75%	
Transformers	15%	
Civil works & Wiring	10%	
87L Differential Line Protection Upgrade		
Switchgears ⁽³⁾	78%	
M&P devices ⁽⁴⁾	12%	
Civil works & Wiring	10%	

(1): Based on 6.6kV MV 3L-NPC SOP converter presented in Table VI.

(2): Outdoor containerized solution (E-house), pre-assembled & tested. Includes liquid-air heat exchangers for PE cooling.

(3): 20 Switchgears (used in several Line, Transformer and Bus-tie positions) with in-built M&P devices pre-assembled & tested. Switchgears installed in specific E-houses with all required internal MV cabling.

(4): Independent M&P devices installed in ABCD heads in two BSPs.

Fig. 14: 10MVA SOP B2B-VSC (left column) and Bus-tie (right column) hosting capacity comparison:
 (First row) - Active power flow through link.
 (Second row) Maximum node voltage in MV circuit.
 (Third row) Maximum branch load in MV circuit.

Only at extreme operation points, where the active power flow of the B2B-VSC makes full use of the apparent power of the converter, is where voltage values reach maximum allowed boundaries. Moreover, the B2B-VSC active power flow dispatch calculated by the optimization algorithm shows very similar to the active power that flows naturally through the bus-tie, the latter being imposed by impedances and angle differences between connection nodes.

Beyond comparisons of two similar alternatives (i.e., B2B-VSC vs. Protections upgrade), analogies between B2B-VSC type solutions and traditional alternatives based on new power line construction require a case-by-case study. Reinforcing (i.e., meshing) a MV circuit by installing a new HV/MV BSP would certainly boost hosting capacity metrics thanks to flattened voltage profiles through enhanced power evacuation paths. However, costs related to such investments are very dependent on the proximity of HV lines. Previously referred environmental constraints can impede project feasibilities. Costs per km of new 132kV power lines (both aerial and cable) can multiple those declared in Table I (30kV) by an average factor of five. HV/MV substations require space as well as the installation of costly HV elements.

2) Effective Grounding and Zero sequence currents

B2B-VSC converter topologies showcased in Table IV are usually connected by means of interface transformers that adapt connection voltages. This approach has been used in previously referred utility-scale projects [12], [13]. So as not to interfere with protection schemes and settings defined by utilities at BSP level, connections across the MV distribution grid are required to have insulated neutral connections at MV side [65]. As regards the LV side of interface transformers, where B2B-VSC converters are connected, insulated (IT) mode is usually adopted. This grounding configuration is typical in applications where supply continuity must be guaranteed and avoids a system trip should a phase to ground fault occur in the power converter (absence of fault current). All in all, transformer-interfaced B2B-VSC solutions with insulated neutral at MV and LV-IT connection are not affected by zero-sequence current flows.

In IT systems that include interface-transformers, preferably built with an electrostatic shield between windings, Common Mode (CM) voltages generated by the power converter are blocked within the LV side, avoiding CM distortion at MV [66]. In such cases, specific metering devices must be used to monitor the insulation level of the LV circuit, detect faulty situations and coordinate protective actions [67]. Typically, such devices are connected at the DC link of VSC converters permitting to detect an insulation failure in both AC sides as well as internally, in the DC bus (Fig 15).

Transformer Less (TL) configurations are technically possible provided the output voltage of the B2B-VSC converter is high enough to allow for its direct connection to the MV mains (e.g., MMC). Focusing on TL multi-level converters, [68] describes different grounding possibilities at either AC or DC side to keep MV CM voltages within permissible values. When it comes to zero-sequence current flows, grounded TL configurations would be affected by them in the presence of disturbances as Single Line Ground faults (SLG). Reference [69] compares different grounding methods (AC zig-zag, AC reactance and DC mid-point) and describes subsequent zero-sequence current flows for a MMC type MVDC power link.

Fig. 15: Insulation monitoring device and area in a transformer interfaced B2B-VSC power link.

Literature identifies different alternatives to minimize zero-sequence current flows in three-phase-four-wire power systems (3P4W). From the use of magnetic components to the application of active compensators based on PE, or combinations thereof. References [70], [71] showcase a comprehensive review of options available.

To finalize, when supplying power to a network that has been insulated, transformer interfaced B2B-VSC power links should adapt the grounding of their MV connection to the utility standard. Worldwide, different neutral grounding strategies are adopted by DSOs that operate three phase MV distribution grids; i.e., Directly grounded, isolated, impedance grounded or resonant circuit grounded [72]. The vector group of the B2B-VSC step-up transformer should therefore be chosen accordingly (i.e., access to neutral point at MV side, if required) and grounding elements as well as protections adapted accordingly. Should the required MV neutral connection be grounded, the most adopted zero-sequence current limiting strategy corresponds to the resonant neutral connection [59], dominant in European territory. Active grounding systems are also industrially available and being adopted at utility scale [59].

VI. CONCLUSION

The overview given in this paper about four cornerstones of B2B-VSC power links permits to have a clear vision of technology readiness, integration requirements and technical limitations of this type of distribution level FACTS. Adequacy of power electronics technology and validity of existing protection schemes have been described in this paper with figures from industrial converters and a real MV network model. Detailed efficiency curves for different SOP type industrial converters have been showcased together with dimensions, costs comparisons and integration characteristics. Backhaul network bottlenecks and its affection to dispatching control strategies have been addressed describing alternatives available for networks that account for low digitalization levels. Related to that, angle difference based autonomous controls used in transmission networks have been highlighted as possible alternatives to be explored also at MV distribution. An exercise, based on the same network model, has allowed carrying out a preliminary assessment of this possibility. Results obtained show angle difference values that might be tracked by B2B-VSC converter controllers. Nevertheless, highest accuracy measurements would be mandatory for that and further research would be required to determine the impact that unavoidable measurement errors would have on the overall performance.

Finally, overall costs of B2B-VSC power links should be addressed considering operational benefits derived from their use. Power electronics and backhaul upgrade costs should be compared to benefits obtained from increased hosting capacity, optimized grid operation and deferral of other type of investments. Projected to different scenarios, this exercise should permit to have a clearer picture of economic feasibility of B2B-VSC power links in business-as-usual projects.

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